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Abstract:

Task 9.3 foresees the study of a novel charge readout scheme for very large liquid-argon time projection chambers named Vertical Drift. This technology avoids using wires to collect the signals of the electrons from charged-particle ionization, at the end of their drift path. Wire planes are instead replaced by stacks of perforated printed circuit boards integrated in charge readout planes of $3 \times 3.3 \text{ m}^2$ placed to cover the surface at the top of the detector. This active surface receives the electrons drifting thanks to a uniform electric field aligned along the vertical axis. The cryogenic ASIC amplifiers used to read the signals are integrated in this layout in front-end cards by hosted-in-cryostat penetrations ‘signal feedthrough chimneys’ which make them accessible from outside during detector operation. The digitization electronics at warm are cabled to warm flanges closing the top part of the chimneys. This technology, which is foreseen to equip the second DUNE Far Detector module, underwent extensive large-scale tests at the CERN Neutrino Platform in 2021-2022. These tests successfully demonstrated its validity. This milestone reports about the work and developments performed on the chimneys.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2023

For more information on AIDAinnova, its partners and contributors please see <http://aidainnova.web.cern.ch/>

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Task 9.3 has been dealing with the developments associated to the demonstration of the Vertical Drift (VD) charge readout technology which is a novel design of LAr TPC (Time Projection Chamber) detectors which is based on the use of perforated printed circuit boards instead of wire planes for the readout of the ionization signals.

The Vertical Drift design is particularly suited to build and instrument exceptionally large LAr detectors in a simpler and cost-effective way. VD is foreseen to be deployed for the second DUNE Far Detector module (FD-2). Task 9.3 focuses on the demonstration of the configuration for the readout of the top-drift volume of FD2 by developing an optimized configuration for the charge readout planes and their associated electronics. The signal feedthrough chimneys are an essential component of this system, which hosts the cryogenic front-end amplifiers at close distance from the charge readout planes but still allowing for their access from outside the detector.

This milestone status report includes the results from an intensive prototyping campaign on the Vertical Drift technology, which was conducted in 2022 by using the infrastructure provided by the CERN Neutrino Platform including a dedicated Cold-Box cryostat of the exact size of a VD charge readout plane unit. This campaign included the development, construction, and operation of ad hoc chimneys for the Cold-Box configuration. The program included the successful tests of the first two charge readout planes of the final layout foreseen for the top drift volume of FD2 and of their associated electronics and signal feedthrough chimneys. In parallel and based on the experience gained with the CERN tests campaign IJCLAB also optimized the layout of the chimneys foreseen for FD2, including 48 or 24 FE cards in larger radius chimneys, for which dedicated engineering prototypes and characterization tests are in progress.

1. INTRODUCTION

Task 9.3 Vertical Drift (VD) Charge Readout is oriented towards detector development for the construction of the second DUNE LAr Far Detector module (FD-2). Vertical Drift is a completely innovative technique that allows reading the ionization of charged tracks in LAr Time Projection Chambers without instrumenting the anode surface with wire planes but by exploiting Charge Readout Plane (CRP) units (each one covering $3 \times 3.3 \text{ m}^2$ active surface) made of two layers of perforated anode Printed Circuit Boards (PCB). The anode perforated PCBs copper layers are segmented in strips of about 5 mm pitch in order to define readout views. The two PCB layers provide two views (at ± 30 degrees) reading the induction signal and a last view at 90 degrees collecting the electrons. The Vertical Drift Layout and the use of perforated anodes instead of wire planes make the construction and installation of these large-scale detectors cheap and effective.

The anode planes are coupled to dedicated cryogenic Front-End (FE) and digitization warm electronics (together defined as: Top Drift Electronics, TDE) explicitly developed and optimized for this configuration, which will be installed in the upper part of the drift volume of the DUNE VD Far Detector module. Special mechanical cryostat penetrations “Chimneys” host the FE boards with cryogenic amplifiers, preserving their accessibility at any time without interfering with the detector operation. Vertical Drift is an evolution and further simplification of the Dual-Phase technique already developed in AIDA2020. The Dual-Phase and Vertical Drift developments have both been strongly supported by the CERN Neutrino Platform infrastructure in the EHN1 hall.

The demonstration at large scale of this unprecedented detector technology corresponding to the Vertical Drift for the DUNE top drift volume of FD-2 is the goal of task 9.3 and it represents an essential step before moving to the construction of the DUNE FD-2. In the years 2021 and 2022, CRP units with perforated anodes were constructed and tested, together with the associated readout electronics and chimneys, at the CERN Neutrino Platform with a dedicated cold-box cryostat, capable of hosting and running in LAr TPC configuration a complete VD CRP.

For this purpose, dedicated chimneys adapted to the cold-box configuration were built and integrated on the Cold-Box cryostat roof. In parallel, the development and prototyping activities aimed at designing the optimized larger chimneys foreseen to be deployed on the cryostat of the DUNE FD-2 saw substantial progress as well. The Chimneys sub-task is an essential ingredient of task 9.3 focused on the developments needed for the VD technology. This milestone reports about the chimney developments which occurred since 2021 and on its integration in the whole goal of demonstration of the Vertical Drift technology, pursued by task 9.3.

2. ACTIVITIES AND RESULTS

2.1. VERTICAL DRIFT COLD-BOX TESTS AND CHIMNEYS INTEGRATION

Vertical Drift Charge Readout Planes (CRPs) with perforated anodes were constructed and tested at the CERN Neutrino Platform with a dedicated Cold-Box (CB) cryostat. The year 2021 saw a very intensive test program at the CERN Neutrino Platform in the EHN1 hall, where a new Cold-Box (CB) cryostat was equipped nearby the NP02 cryostat, in order to share the same cryogenic system, for the tests of the Vertical Drift CRPs [1]. The Cold-Box has exactly the footprint capable of containing a single CRP module. The CB can operate in Time Projection Chamber configuration with 30 cm vertical drift between the CRP and the cathode plane. This drift distance allows collecting very large samples (order of millions) of cosmic rays that can be exploited to fully characterize the CRP behavior and of its associated electronics, both covered by task 9.3. The CRP is suspended from the roof of the Cold-Box that can be inserted and extracted from the top to seal the detector configuration.

Five small signal feedthrough chimneys, each one capable of containing up to 10 Front-End (FE) cryogenic cards with ASIC amplifiers (with 64 readout channels per card), were designed and customized in 2021 by IJCLAB in order to be integrated in the Cold-Box roof for the Vertical Drift tests. The chimneys were then successfully operated in 2021-2022 together with the CRP and the associated readout electronics. The FE cards were mounted on vertical FR4 blades allowing their access via insertion and extraction of the blades in/from the chimneys. The blades slide precisely in vertical guides built in the inner structure of the chimney which drive the FE cards precisely to the insertion positions on the connectors present at the bottom of the chimneys. The setup was operational and demonstrated all functionalities including the ones related to the chimneys such as the operation of the FE electronics and its insertion/extraction.

Fig. 1 Cryogenic front-end card with four ASIC amplifiers mounted and cabled on a FR4 blade allowing for its insertion/extraction in the chimney.

The concept of the chimneys, as an essential interface component between the CRP and its readout electronics, is illustrated in Fig.2. The chimneys are pipes going through the insulation of the roof of the cryostat until they reach a location, inside the cryostat gas ullage, very close to the CRP. The bottom of the chimney is sealed by a cold flange printed circuit board (Fig. 3) which prevents contaminating the ultra-pure LAr environment of the cryostat during access to the FE electronics or chimney operation. The FE cards with the cryogenic amplifiers, mounted on blades, are plugged on connectors located on the top surface of the cold flange PCB. The bottom side of the cold flange has connectors which are used to plug flat cables bringing the signals (from charge collection or induction views) from the CRP. The FE cards operate at a temperature of about 110 K present in the cryostat ullage space. The chimney is closed at the top with a vertical warm flange which includes the connector to cable the amplified signals to the digitization electronics contained in uTCA crates on the cryostat roof and it is filled with N₂ to avoid humidity condensation on the FE cards.

Fig. 2 (Left) Illustration of a signal feedthrough chimney hosting the cryogenic amplifiers and going through the cryostat insulation (closed view and section of the chimney pipe showing the blade with the FE card plugged on the cold flange) (Right) view of the top of the system for the current implementation in the Cold-Box tests for the Vertical Drift.

Fig. 3 (Left) cryogenic FE cards with ASIC amplifiers (seen from the chimney side and not mounted on blades) plugged for illustrative purposes into the top side of a cold flange dismantled from a chimney (Right) three Cold-Box chimneys during an integration test with the uTCA digitization system in summer 2021 prior to the Cold-Box integration.

The first CRP prototype (CRP1) was successfully tested in November-December 2021. This CRP was shared among the top-drift, on which task 9.3 is focused, (TDE) and bottom-drift (BDE) readouts developed for the DUNE Vertical Drift Far Detector module.

Following this first test, the channels layout and strip orientation (Fig.4) were finalized for the final top-drift and bottom-drift CRPs. The channels counting corresponds to 48 FE cards per CRP (3072 readout channels). The first full-size top-drift CRP (CRP2) was then constructed and tested in July 2022 during the continuation of the cold box tests campaign foreseen in 2022. A second first full-size top-drift CRP (CRP3), with the same strip layout of CRP2, was also fully tested in October 2022.

Fig. 4 Final layout of the strip segmentation implemented on the stack of anode perforated PCBs constituting CRP2.

Fig. 5 (Left) CRP2 suspended from the Cold-Box cover during installation and (Right) Cold-Box roof top view during CRP2 operation with 5 chimneys each one cabled to a uTCA digitization crate (black boxes)

In 2022 the Cold-Box tests of the final CRP layout demonstrated the reliable performance of the CRP and of its associated electronics, including the operation of the chimneys. The results were completely fulfilling expectations. A very large sample of cosmic ray tracks was collected to characterize the stable operation of the detector. A typical event containing cosmic ray tracks is shown in Fig. 6. This test program fully demonstrated the Vertical Drift readout.

Fig. 6 Example of clean cosmic ray tracks collected during the operation of CRP2 in the Cold-Box.

2.2. DESIGN AND PROTOTYPING OF OPTIMIZED LARGE DIAMETER CHIMNEYS FOR FD2

Given the final CRP strips layout corresponding to 48 FE cards and the experience accumulated with the Cold-Box, chimney design was further developed and optimized in 2022 for FD-2 to exploit larger chimneys capable of containing all the 48 cards needed to read out a CRP module.

Chimneys of this size are too large to be implemented in the Cold-Box roof and are an evolution of the 10-card chimneys already exploited for the Cold-Box tests, inheriting from their design. Their development followed then a parallel path to the Cold-Box tests. The design is based on the same concepts already exploited for the cold flange, the warm flanges, and the blades. The larger chimneys optimize the costs and reduce the number of penetrations needed on the FD-2 cryostat roof.

Design activities performed at IJCLAB included the FD-2 cryostat interface aspects and installation aspects as well as thermal simulations (see Fig.9). Each 48-card chimney is foreseen to be located at the vertex common to four CRP modules and to then collect the signals from the corresponding four independent CRP quarters. This configuration is common to the 63 chimneys placed at the centre of the cryostat. The 42 chimneys located at the periphery, due to a border effect in the cabling to the CRPs, include only 24 cards needed for the readout of two CRP quarters and have a smaller radius as a result.

The FD-2 cryostat roof layout including the positions of the chimneys is shown in Fig.7.

Fig. 7 Optimized penetrations layout foreseen for the 48 and 24 FE cards chimneys on the roof of FD-2 cryostat.

The CAD models of the two kinds of chimneys are presented in Fig. 8. Both the 48 and 24 cards chimneys use the same warm flanges for the cabling to the uTCA digitization electronics. The 48-card model has two warm flanges in a V-shape configuration. The 24-card model has a single warm flange. The open bottom views in the two cases in Fig. 8 allow seeing the location of the FE cards.

Fig. 8 CAD models of the optimized 48 and 24 cards chimneys designed for FD2.

Prototyping activities were launched in 2022, starting first with the 24-card chimney, which has a more complicated and packed layout of the FE cards to fully exploit the available surface on the cold flange (see Fig. 9). The 24-card prototype tests and characterization are foreseen to be completed in 2023 when also the 48-card model is foreseen to be built and tested.

Fig. 9 (Left) COMSOL thermal simulations for a 24-card chimney (Right) cold flange of a 24-card chimney produced during the prototyping activities.

3. REFERENCES

[1] NP02 Collaboration (2022) *Yearly progress report on NP02* CERN-SPSC-2022-014; SPSC-SR-308 (2022) <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2805710>

ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
ASIC	Application Specific Integrated Circuit
CB	Cold-Box cryostat/Time Projection Chamber
CRP	Charge Readout Plane (3x3.3m ² readout unit of Vertical Drift)
DUNE	Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment
FD-2	Second DUNE Far Detector module (15 kton active LAr mass)
FE	Front-End
FR4	Flame Retardant 4 (PCB material)
LAr	Liquid Argon
PCB	Printed Circuit Board
TDE	Top Drift Electronics
TPC	Time Projection Chamber
VD	Vertical Drift